

This publication was funded by the European Union. Its contents are the sole responsibility of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Union.

Grant Agreement number	101094014
Project Acronym	BLUE4ALL
Project title	Blueprint demonstration for co-created effective, efficient and resilient networks of MPAs
Deliverable title:	BLUE4ALL project governance structure
Deliverable number	7.4.
Deliverable version	1
Contractual date of delivery	28/02/2023
Actual date of delivery	28/02/2023
Document status	Final
Document version	1
Diffusion	Public
Nature of Deliverable	Report
Work Package	7
Partner responsible	RBINS
Contributing Partners	Submariner
Author(s)	Bob Rumes (RBINS)
Reviewers	Ivana Stojanovic (SUB), Steven Degraer (RBINS)
Approved by	Project Officer
Abstract	This deliverable (project governance structure) describes the legal, contractual, financial and administrative management practices of the project, in compliance with the contractual obligations, good management practices and the provisions of the Consortium Agreement and release of end reports.
Keywords	Project governance, Core governance, Call management, Consortium Coordination

This publication was funded by the European Union. Its contents are the sole responsibility of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Union.

Acronyms

Advisory Board (AB)

Consortium Agreement (CA)

Coordination Team (CT)

European Commission (EC)

European Union (EU)

General Assembly (GA)

Horizon Europe (HEU)

Marine Protected Area (MPA)

Non-Disclosure Agreement (NDA)

Work Package (WP)

Work Package Leaders (WPL)

This publication was funded by the European Union. Its contents are the sole responsibility of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Union.

Table of Contents

1. Introduction	4
2. General operational procedures for all Consortium Bodies	5
2.1 Representation in meetings	5
2.2 Preparation and organisation of meetings	5
2.3 Voting rules and quorum	6
2.4 Veto rights.....	7
2.5 Minutes of meetings	8
3. Specific operational procedures for the Consortium Bodies.....	8
3.1 General Assembly.....	8
3.2 Coordination Team	10
4. Coordinator	12
4.1 Responsibilities	12
4.3 Replacement	12
4.4 Limitations.....	12
5. Work Package Leaders (WPL)	13
6. Advisory Board (AB)	13
7. Annex A: NDA for AB members	14

This publication was funded by the European Union. Its contents are the sole responsibility of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Union.

1. Introduction

This document is developed as part of the BLUE4ALL project (Blueprint demonstration for co-created effective, efficient and resilient networks of MPAs), which has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme, under the Grant Agreement number 101094014. The project governance structure represents Deliverable 7.4 of Work Package 7 – Project coordination and management. Issues examined under this deliverable include the description of the governance structure, which is further elaborated in the Consortium Agreement (CA) and which provides the profile and responsibilities of the different Consortium Bodies: Coordinator, General Assembly, Coordination Team and the Advisory Board. This document is to be interpreted with reference to the Grant Agreement (GA) and the CA.

The organisational structure of the BLUE4ALL consortium comprises the following Consortium Bodies (Figure 1).

- The General Assembly (GA) as the ultimate decision-making body of the consortium;
- The Coordination Team (CT) as the supervisory body for the execution of the Project, which shall report to and be accountable to the General Assembly;
- The Advisory Board (AB) which will validate the applicability of the project outcomes to achieving the EU Mission;
- The Coordinator as the legal entity acting as the intermediary between the Parties and the Granting Authority. The Coordinator shall, in addition to its responsibilities as a Party, perform the tasks assigned to it as described in the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement.

Figure 1. BLUE4ALL governance structure overview

This publication was funded by the European Union. Its contents are the sole responsibility of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Union.

2. General operational procedures for all Consortium Bodies

2.1 Representation in meetings

Any Party which is appointed to take part in a Consortium Body shall designate one representative (hereinafter referred to as "Member").

Any Member:

- should be present or represented at any meeting;
- may appoint a substitute or a proxy to attend and vote at any meeting;

and shall participate in a cooperative manner in the meetings.

2.2 Preparation and organisation of meetings

2.2.1 Convening meetings

The chairperson of a Consortium Body shall convene meetings of that Consortium Body.

	Ordinary meeting	Extraordinary meeting
General Assembly	At least once a year	At any time upon request of the Coordination Team or 1/3 of the Members of the General Assembly
Coordination Team	At least quarterly	At any time upon request of any Member of the Coordination Team
Advisory Board	At least once a year in combination with the General Assembly meetings	At any time upon written request of any two Members of the Advisory Board

2.2.2 Notice of a meeting

The chairperson of a Consortium Body shall give written notice of a meeting to each Member of that Consortium Body as soon as possible and no later than the minimum number of days preceding the meeting as indicated below.

	Ordinary meeting	Extraordinary meeting
General Assembly	45 calendar days	15 calendar days
Coordination Team	14 calendar days	7 calendar days
Advisory Board	45 calendar days	15 calendar days

2.2.3 Sending the agenda

The chairperson of a Consortium Body shall prepare and send each Member of that Consortium Body an agenda no later than the minimum number of days preceding the meeting as indicated below.

General Assembly	21 calendar days, 10 calendar days for an extraordinary meeting
Coordination Team	7 calendar days
Advisory Board	21 calendar days, 10 calendar days for an extraordinary meeting

This publication was funded by the European Union. Its contents are the sole responsibility of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Union.

2.2.4 Adding agenda items

Any agenda item requiring a decision by the Members of a Consortium Body must be identified as such on the agenda.

Any Member of a Consortium Body may add an item to the original agenda by written notice to all of the other Members of that Consortium Body up to the minimum number of days preceding the meeting as indicated below.

General Assembly	14 calendar days, 7 calendar days for an extraordinary meeting
Coordination Team	2 calendar days
Advisory Board	14 calendar days, 7 calendar days for an extraordinary meeting

During a meeting the Members of a Consortium Body present or represented can unanimously agree to add a new item to the original agenda.

Meetings of each Consortium Body may also be held by tele- or videoconference, or other telecommunication means.

Decisions will only be binding once the relevant part of the minutes has been accepted according to Section **Error! Reference source not found.**

2.2.5 Decisions without a meeting

Any decision may also be taken without a meeting if

- a) the Coordinator circulates to all Members of the General Assembly a suggested decision with a deadline for responses of at least 10 calendar days after receipt by a Party and
- b) the decision is agreed by 51 % of all Parties.

The Coordinator shall inform all the Parties of the outcome of the vote.

A veto according to Section 0 may be submitted up to 15 calendar days after receipt of this information.

The decision will be binding after the Coordinator sends a notification to all Members. The Coordinator will keep records of the votes and make them available to the Parties on request.

2.3 Voting rules and quorum

2.3.1

Each Consortium Body shall not deliberate and decide validly in meetings unless two-thirds (2/3) of its Members are present or represented (quorum).

If the quorum is not reached, the chairperson of the Consortium Body shall convene another ordinary meeting within 15 calendar days. If in this meeting the quorum is not reached once more, the chairperson shall convene an extraordinary meeting which shall be entitled to decide even if less than the quorum of Members is present or represented.

This publication was funded by the European Union. Its contents are the sole responsibility of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Union.

2.3.2

Each Member of a Consortium Body present or represented in the meeting shall have one vote. Associated Partners are excluded from certain decisions of the General Assembly according to Section 3.1.1.4.

2.3.3

A Party which the General Assembly has declared according to Section **Error! Reference source not found.** to be a Defaulting Party may not vote.

2.3.4

Decisions shall be taken by a majority of two-thirds (2/3) of the votes cast. In case two-thirds (2/3) do not represent a whole number, the number of votes representing the subsequent whole number will be required (for example, 2/3 of 20 votes equals to 13.33 and in such case, the affirmative vote of 14 members will be required to pass a resolution).

2.4 Veto rights

2.4.1

A Party which can show that its own work, time for performance, costs, liabilities, intellectual property rights or other legitimate interests would be severely affected by a decision of a Consortium Body may exercise a veto with respect to the corresponding decision or relevant part of the decision.

2.4.2

When the decision is foreseen on the original agenda, a Party may only veto such a decision during the meeting.

2.4.3

When a decision has been taken on a new item added to the agenda before or during the meeting, a Party may veto such decision during the meeting or within 15 calendar days after receipt of the draft minutes of the meeting.

A Party that is not appointed to participate to a particular Consortium Body may veto a decision within the same number of calendar days after receipt of the draft minutes of the meeting.

2.4.4

When a decision has been taken without a meeting, a Party may veto such decision within 15 calendar days after written notice by the chairperson of the outcome of the vote.

2.4.5

In case of exercise of veto, the Members of the related Consortium Body shall make every effort to resolve the matter which occasioned the veto to the general satisfaction of all the Parties.

2.4.6

A Party may neither veto decisions relating to its identification to be in breach of its obligations nor to its identification as a Defaulting Party. The Defaulting Party may not veto decisions relating to its participation and termination in the consortium or the consequences of them.

This publication was funded by the European Union. Its contents are the sole responsibility of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Union.

2.4.7

A Party requesting to leave the consortium may not veto decisions relating thereto.

2.5 Minutes of meetings

2.5.1

The chairperson of a Consortium Body shall produce minutes of each meeting which shall be the formal record of all decisions taken. He/she shall send the draft minutes to all Members within 10 calendar days of the meeting.

2.5.2

The minutes shall be considered as accepted if, within 15 calendar days from receipt, no Member has sent an objection by written notice to the chairperson with respect to the accuracy of the draft of the minutes by written notice.

2.5.3

The chairperson shall send the accepted minutes to all the Parties and to the Coordinator, who shall retain copies of them.

3. Specific operational procedures for the Consortium Bodies

3.1 General Assembly

In addition to the rules described in Section 2, the following rules apply:

3.1.1 Members

3.1.1.1

The General Assembly shall consist of one representative of each Party (hereinafter General Assembly Member).

3.1.1.2

Each General Assembly Member shall be deemed to be duly authorised to deliberate, negotiate and decide on all matters listed in Section 6.3.1.2. of the Consortium Agreement.

3.1.1.3

The Coordinator shall chair all meetings of the General Assembly, unless decided otherwise in a meeting of the General Assembly.

3.1.1.4

The Parties agree to abide by all decisions of the General Assembly. This does not prevent the Parties from exercising their veto rights, according to Section 2.4.1, or from submitting a dispute to resolution in accordance with the provisions of Settlement of disputes as described in Section 11.8 of the Consortium Agreement.

The Associated Partners are excluded from voting on and vetoing the following decisions of the General Assembly (3.1.2) and therefore are not counted towards any respective quorum:

This publication was funded by the European Union. Its contents are the sole responsibility of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Union.

- Financial changes to the Consortium Plan
- Distribution of EU contribution among the Beneficiaries
- Proposals for changes to Annex 2 of the Grant Agreement to be agreed by the Granting Authority
- Decisions related to Section 7.1.4 of the Consortium Agreement

Regarding unanimity or majority decisions, only Members with voting rights regarding the item are taken into account (e.g. Section 2.2.8).

3.1.2 Decisions

The General Assembly shall be free to act on its own initiative to formulate proposals and take decisions in accordance with the procedures set out herein.

In addition, all proposals made by the Coordination Team shall also be considered and decided upon by the General Assembly.

The following decisions shall be taken by the General Assembly:

Content, finances and intellectual property rights

- Proposals for changes to Annexes 1 and 2 of the Grant Agreement to be agreed by the Granting Authority
- Changes to the Consortium Plan
- Modifications or withdrawal of Background in Attachment 1 (Background Included)
- Additions to Attachment 3 of the Consortium Agreement (List of Third Parties for simplified transfer according to Section **Error! Reference source not found.**)
- Additions to Attachment 4 of the Consortium Agreement (Identified entities under the same control)

Evolution of the consortium

- Entry of a new Party to the Project and approval of the settlement on the conditions of the accession of such a new Party
- Withdrawal of a Party from the Project and the approval of the settlement on the conditions of the withdrawal
- Identification of a breach by a Party of its obligations under the Consortium Agreement or the Grant Agreement
- Declaration of a Party to be a Defaulting Party
- Remedies to be performed by a Defaulting Party
- Termination of a Defaulting Party's participation in the Project and measures relating thereto
- Proposal to the Granting Authority for a change of the Coordinator
- Proposal to the Granting Authority for suspension of all or part of the Project

This publication was funded by the European Union. Its contents are the sole responsibility of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Union.

- Proposal to the Granting Authority for termination of the Project and the Consortium Agreement
- Steps to be taken for litigation purposes and the coverage of litigation costs in case of joint claims of the parties of the consortium against a Party (Section 4.2, Section 7.1.4)

Appointments

On the basis of the Grant Agreement, the appointment if necessary of:

- Coordination Team Members
- External Expert Advisory Board Members to the Advisory Board (AB)

In the case of abolished tasks as a result of a decision of the General Assembly, Members shall rearrange the tasks of the Parties concerned. Such rearrangement shall take into consideration any prior legitimate commitments which cannot be cancelled.

3.2 Coordination Team

In addition to the rules in Section **Error! Reference source not found.**, the following rules shall apply:

3.2.1 Members

The Coordination Team shall consist of WP-leaders and the Coordinator. Each Party, including the Coordinator, shall have one vote. Notwithstanding the foregoing, in the event of a tied vote, the Coordinator shall have a casting vote.

The Coordinator shall chair all meetings of the Coordination Team, unless decided otherwise by a majority of two-thirds of the members of the Coordination Team.

3.2.2 Minutes of meetings

Minutes of Coordination Team meetings, once accepted, shall be sent by the Coordinator to the General Assembly Members for information.

3.2.3 Tasks

3.2.3.1

The Coordination Team shall prepare meetings, propose decisions and prepare the agenda of the General Assembly according to Section 0.

3.2.3.2

The Coordination Team shall seek a consensus among the Parties.

3.2.3.3

The Coordination Team shall be responsible for the proper execution and implementation of the decisions of the General Assembly.

3.2.3.4

The Coordination Team shall monitor the effective and efficient implementation of the Project.

This publication was funded by the European Union. Its contents are the sole responsibility of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Union.

3.2.3.5

In addition, the Coordination Team shall collect information at least every 6 months on the progress of the Project, examine that information to assess the compliance of the Project with the Consortium Plan and, if necessary, propose modifications of the Consortium Plan to the General Assembly.

3.2.3.6

The Coordination Team shall:

- support the Coordinator in preparing meetings with the Granting Authority and in preparing related data and deliverables
- prepare the content and timing of press releases and joint publications by the consortium or proposed by the Granting Authority in respect of the procedures of the Grant Agreement Article 17 and Annex 5 Section “Communication, Dissemination, Open Science and Visibility” and of Section **Error! Reference source not found.** of the Consortium Agreement.

3.2.3.7

In the case of abolished tasks as a result of a decision of the General Assembly, the Coordination Team shall advise the General Assembly on ways to rearrange tasks and budgets of the Parties concerned. Such rearrangement shall take into consideration any prior legitimate commitments which cannot be cancelled.

This publication was funded by the European Union. Its contents are the sole responsibility of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Union.

4. Coordinator

4.1 Responsibilities

The Coordinator shall be the intermediary between the Parties and the Granting Authority and shall perform all tasks assigned to it as described in the Grant Agreement and in the Consortium Agreement.

In particular, the Coordinator shall be responsible for:

- monitoring compliance by the Parties with their obligations under the Consortium Agreement and the Grant Agreement
- keeping the address list of Members and other contact persons updated and available
- collecting, reviewing to verify consistency and submitting reports, other deliverables (including financial statements and related certifications) and specific requested documents to the Granting Authority
- transmitting documents and information connected with the Project to any other Parties concerned
- administering the financial contribution of the Granting Authority and fulfilling the financial tasks described in Section **Error! Reference source not found.**
- providing, upon request, the Parties with official copies or originals of documents that are in the sole possession of the Coordinator when such copies or originals are necessary for the Parties to present claims
- the overall project coordination, assuring strategic guidance and effective internal communication within the Consortium and the European Commission
- providing a copy of the Grant Agreement and its Annexes to the Associated Partners.

If one or more of the Parties is late in submission of any Project deliverable, the Coordinator may nevertheless submit the other 'Parties' Project deliverables and all other documents required by the Grant Agreement to the Granting Authority in time.

4.3 Replacement

If the Coordinator fails in its coordination tasks, the General Assembly may propose to the Granting Authority to change the Coordinator.

4.4 Limitations

The Coordinator shall not be entitled to act or to make legally binding declarations on behalf of any other Party or of the consortium, unless explicitly stated otherwise in the Grant Agreement or the Consortium Agreement.

The Coordinator shall not enlarge its role beyond the tasks specified in the Consortium Agreement and in the Grant Agreement.

This publication was funded by the European Union. Its contents are the sole responsibility of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Union.

5. Work Package Leaders (WPL)

The WPLs shall

- Initiate, coordinate, and organize their WPs, including the timely delivery and assurance of quality of all deliverables, reports and outputs of their respective WPs
- Collect information on the progress of the tasks within the WP and deliver this to the Coordinator
- Examine the information to assess the compliance with the Project and the work tasks described in the WP
- Formulate an implementation plan for the activities within the WP for coming periods
- Inform the Coordinator and propose possible fallback scenarios in case of major deviations from the work plan that have an impact on the objective of the WP and/or the Project
- Support the Coordinator in preparing related data and deliverables

6. Advisory Board (AB)

An Advisory Board (AB) will be appointed and steered by the Coordination Team. The AB shall assist and facilitate the decisions made by the General Assembly. The Advisory Board will be continuously engaged to validate the applicability of the project actions and outcomes to achieving the EU MISSION on “Restore our Oceans and Waters by 2030”.

The Coordinator will ensure that a Non-Disclosure Agreement (NDA) is executed between all Parties and each AB member.

By way of exception to Section **Error! Reference source not found.** above, the Parties mandate the Coordinator to execute, in their name and on their behalf, an NDA with each member of the AB, in order to protect Confidential Information disclosed by any of the Parties to any member of the AB, either directly or through the Coordinator in the case where the concerned Party gave to the Coordinator its prior written approval for such disclosure. The NDA for the AB members is enclosed in Annex A. The mandate of the Coordinator comprises solely the execution of the NDA in Annex A.

Its terms shall be not less stringent than those stipulated in the Consortium Agreement, and it shall be concluded no later than 30 calendar days after their nomination or before any confidential information will be exchanged/disclosed, whichever date is earlier. The Coordinator shall write the minutes of the AB meetings and submit them to the General Assembly. The AB members shall be allowed to participate in General Assembly meetings upon invitation but they do not have any voting rights.

This publication was funded by the European Union. Its contents are the sole responsibility of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Union.

7. Annex A: NDA for AB members

NON-DISCLOSURE AGREEMENT for Advisory Board (AB) member

THIS AGREEMENT [*the Agreement*] is entered into on this [*insert number of day*] day of [*insert Month and year*] by and between:

1. RBINS (Coordinator) on behalf of the Consortium of Project 101094014 - BLUE4ALL – hereinafter referred to as [the Discloser]

and

2. [*Insert official name of the AB member*], having its registered office or based in [*insert the Legal Address of the Entity*] hereinafter referred to as [the Recipient]

WHEREAS:

The Discloser and Recipient hereto desire to work together in the collaborative project in response to the call HORIZON-MISS-2021-OCEAN-02 under the HORIZON Innovation Actions with the project number 101094014 and project acronym BLUE4ALL.

Throughout the aforementioned discussions, the Discloser may share proprietary information or Confidential Information with the Recipient subject to the terms and covenants set forth below.

Whereas the Discloser may disclose, upon their specific written approval and under the conditions set out in the Consortium Agreement, confidential information of the other partners of the BLUE4ALL project (the “Partners”).

NOW IT IS AGREED AS FOLLOWS:

1. Confidential Information

1. Discloser and Recipient

For the purposes of this agreement, ‘Discloser’ shall mean the party which discloses its Confidential Information (as defined below). The Recipient shall mean the party to whom Confidential Information is disclosed.

2. Confidential Information

2.1 For the purposes of this Agreement, Confidential Information means any data or proprietary information (i) of the Discloser, or (ii) of the Partners insofar as the Discloser is allowed to, that is not generally known to the public or has not yet been revealed, whether in tangible or intangible form, whenever and however disclosed, including, but not limited to: (i) any scientific or technical information,

This publication was funded by the European Union. Its contents are the sole responsibility of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Union.

invention, design, process, procedure, formula, improvement, technology or method; (ii) any concepts, samples, reports, data, know-how, works-in-progress, designs, drawings, photographs, development tools, specifications, software programs, source code, object code, flow charts, and databases; (iii) any marketing strategies, plans, financial information, projections, operations, sales estimates, business plans and performance results relating to the Discloser's or Partners' past, present or future business activities, or those of its affiliates, subsidiaries and affiliated companies; (iv) trade secrets; plans for products or services, and customer or supplier lists; (v) any other information that should reasonably be recognized as Confidential Information by the Recipient.

2.2 The Discloser and the Recipient agree hereby that Confidential Information needs not to be novel, unique, patentable, copyrightable or constitutes a trade secret in order to be designated Confidential Information and therefore protected.

2.3 The Recipient hereby acknowledge that the Confidential Information proprietary of the Discloser or the Partners has been developed and obtained through great efforts and shall be regarded and kept as Confidential Information.

2.4 Notwithstanding the aforementioned Confidential Information shall exclude information that: (i) is already in the public domain at the time of disclosure by the Discloser to the Recipient or thereafter enters the public domain without any breach of the terms of this Agreement; (ii) was already known by the Recipient before the moment of disclosure (under evidence of reasonable proof or written record of such disclosure); (iii) is subsequently communicated to the Recipient without any obligation of confidence from a third party who is in lawful possession thereof and under no obligation of confidence to the Discloser; (iv) becomes publicly available by other means than a breach of the confidentiality obligations by the Recipient (not through fault or failure to act by the Recipient); (iv) is or has been developed independently by employees, consultants or agents of the Recipient (proved by reasonable means) without violation of the terms of this Agreement or reference or access to any Confidential Information pertaining to the Discloser.

3. Purpose of the Disclosure of Confidential Information

The Discloser and Recipient will enter on discussions regarding collaboration toward the Europeanfunded Project BLUE4ALL in the field of "Marine and Ocean Management, Marine Conservation, Marine Protected Areas/MPAs", in the scope of the Recipient being a member of the Advisory Board (AB) of the BLUE4ALL project.

4. Undertakings of the Recipient

4.1 In the context of discussions, preparations or negotiations, the Discloser may disclose Confidential Information to the Recipient. The Recipient agrees to use the Confidential Information solely in the framework of its role as a member of the Advisory Board (AB) of the BLUE4ALL project and not to use it for any other purpose or without the prior written consent of the Discloser.

4.2 The Recipient will not disclose and will keep confidential the information received, except to its employees, representatives or agents who need to have access to the Confidential Information for the

This publication was funded by the European Union. Its contents are the sole responsibility of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Union.

purpose of carrying out their duties in connection with the permitted purposes specified in clause 2. The Recipient will inform them about the confidential quality of the information provided and will ensure that their agreement is obtained to keep it confidential on the same terms as set forth in this Agreement. Hence the Recipient will be responsible for ensuring that the obligations of confidentiality and non-use contained herein will be strictly observed and will assume full liability for the acts or omissions made for its personnel representatives or agents.

4.3 The Recipient will use the Confidential Information exclusively for the permitted purpose stated in clause 2 and not use the information for its own purposes or benefit.

4.4 The Recipient will not disclose any Confidential Information received to any third parties, except as otherwise provided for herein.

4.5 The Recipient shall treat all Confidential Information with the same degree of care as it accords to its own Confidential Information.

4.6 All Confidential Information disclosed under this Agreement shall be and remain under the property of the Discloser or the Partners and nothing contained in this Agreement shall be construed as granting or conferring any rights to such Confidential Information on the Recipient. Principally, nothing in this Agreement shall be deemed to grant to the Recipient a licence expressly or by implication under any patent, copyright or other intellectual property right. The Recipient hereby acknowledges and confirms that all the existing and future intellectual property rights related to the Confidential Information are exclusive titles of the Discloser or the Partners. For the sake of clarity based in good faith, the Recipient will not apply for or obtain any intellectual property protection in respect of the Confidential Information received. Likewise any modifications and improvements thereof by the Recipient shall be the sole property of the Discloser.

4.7 The Recipient shall promptly return or destroy all copies (in whatever form reproduced or stored), including all notes and derivatives of the Confidential Information disclosed under this Agreement, upon the earlier of (i) the completion or termination of the dealings contemplated in this Agreement; (ii) or the termination of this Agreement; (iii) or at the time the Discloser may request it to the Recipient.

4.8 Notwithstanding the foregoing, the Recipient may retain such of its documents as required to comply with mandatory law, provided that such Confidentiality Information or copies thereof shall be subject to an indefinite confidentiality obligation.

4.9 In the event that the Recipient is asked to communicate the Confidential Information to any judicial, administrative, regulatory authority or similar or obliged to reveal such information by mandatory law, it shall notify promptly the Discloser of the terms of such disclosure and will collaborate to the extent practicable with the Discloser in order to comply with the order and preserve the confidentiality of the Confidential Information.

4.10 The Recipient agrees that the Discloser will suffer irreparable damage if its Confidential Information is made public, released to a third party, or otherwise disclosed in breach of this Agreement and that the Discloser shall be entitled to obtain injunctive relief against a threatened breach or continuation of any

This publication was funded by the European Union. Its contents are the sole responsibility of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Union.

such a breach and, in the event of such breach, an award of actual and exemplary damages from any court of competent jurisdiction.

4.11 The Recipient shall immediately notify upon becoming aware of any breach of confidence by anybody to whom it has disclosed the Confidential Information and give all necessary assistance in connection with any steps which the Discloser may wish to take prevent, stop or obtain compensation for such a breach or threatened breach.

4.12 The Confidential Information subject to this Agreement is made available "as such" and no warranties of any kind are granted or implied with respect to the quality of such information including but not limited to, its applicability for any purpose, noninfringement of third-party rights, accuracy, completeness or correctness. Further, the Discloser or the Partners shall not have any liability to the Recipient resulting from any use of the Confidential Information.

4.13 The Discloser or the Partners are not under any obligation under this Agreement to disclose any Confidential Information it chooses not to disclose.

4.14 Nothing in this Agreement shall be construed to constitute an agency, partnership, joint venture, or other similar relationship between the Discloser and Recipient.

5. Miscellaneous

5.1 Duration and Termination

5.1.1 This Agreement shall remain in effect for a term of 4 years. Notwithstanding the foregoing, the Recipient's duty to hold in confidence Confidential Information that was disclosed during the term shall remain in effect indefinitely, save otherwise agreed.

5.2 Applicable Law and Jurisdiction

This Agreement shall be construed and interpreted by the laws of Belgium. The court of Belgium shall have jurisdiction.

5.3 Validity

If any provisions of this Agreement are invalid or unenforceable, the validity of the remaining provisions shall not be affected. The invalid or unenforceable provision shall be replaced by a valid and enforceable provision that will meet the purpose of the invalid or unenforceable provision as closely as possible.

5.4 Subsequent Agreements

Ancillary agreements, amendments or additions hereto shall be made in writing.

5.5 Communications

This publication was funded by the European Union. Its contents are the sole responsibility of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Union.

Any notices or communications required may be delivered by hand or e-mail, mailed by registered mail to the address of the Recipient/Discloser as indicated above. Any subsequent modification of addresses should be reasonably communicated in advance to the effect of this Agreement.

IN WITNESS WHEREOF, the Parties hereto have caused this Non-Disclosure Agreement to be executed as of the date stated above.

FOR RBINS (Coordinator) on behalf of the Consortium of Project 101094014 - BLUE4ALL

Signature:

[insert name of representative]

[insert title]

[*place*] on [*date*]

FOR [*insert name of participant or potential or current partner*]

Signature:

[insert name of representative]

[insert title]

[*place*] on [*date*]